

18. Uluslararası Güncel Araştırmalarla Sosyal Bilimler Kongresi Tam Metinleri
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ÖN SÖZ

18. Uluslararası Güncel Araştırmalarla Sosyal Bilimler Kongresi, 08-11 Ekim 2024 tarihlerinde Ankara'da gerçekleşecektir. Bu kongre, Saybilder Topluluğunun organizasyonunda ve başta Ankara Hacı Bayram Veli Üniversitesi, Mardin Artuklu Üniversitesi, Carthage University olmak üzere çeşitli yükseköğretim kurumlarının ilmi desteği ile düzenlenmektedir. Kongreye 6 farklı ülkeden davetli konuşmacı davet edilmiştir. Aynı zamanda Türkçe, İngilizce ve Arapça duyurular yapılarak bilim insanlarına çağrıda bulunulmuştur. Bu çağrılar sonrasında Türkiye hariç 12 farklı ülkeden (Birleşik Arap Emirlikleri, Cezayir, Fas, Irak, Katar, Kazakistan, Libya, Mısır, Suudi Arabistan Krallığı, Tunus, Umman, Ürdün) sözlü bildiri kongre programına dâhil edilmiştir. Tüm bildiriler kör hakemlik sürecinden geçirildikten sonra sunuma kabul veya reddi gerçekleştirilmiştir. Bu süreç içerisinde bildirilerin önemli bir kısmına hakemlerden düzeltme talebi gelmiştir. Hakemler tarafından talep edilen düzeltmelerin yapılıp yapılmadığı da özenle kontrol edilmiş ve düzeltilerden sonra kabul mektupları düzenlenerek yazarlarına gönderilmiştir.

Başvuru süreci sonucunda 73'ü Türk bilim insanları tarafından ve 77'si farklı ülkelerden katılan bilim insanları tarafından hazırlanmış toplam 150 bildiri sözlü sunuma uygun bulunmuştur. Bu kitapta kongrede sunulan bildirilere ait tam metinler yer almaktadır.

Kongrenin bilim insanları arasındaki iletişimi kuvvetlendirmesini, bilgi alışverişini arttırmasını, ortak çalışma zeminlerini oluşturmasını, milletimize, insanlığa ve bilgiyle amel edenlere faydalı olmasını diliyorum.

Prof. Dr. Hüseyin Akyüz
Düzenleme Kurulu Başkanı

مقدمة

يسرنا أن نقدم لكم هذا الكتاب الذي يضم مجموعة الأبحاث الكاملة التي قُدمت خلال فعاليات المؤتمر الدولي الثامن عشر للدراسات الاجتماعية والتاريخية والقانونية، الذي عُقد في العاصمة التركية أنقرة خلال الفترة من 8 إلى 11 أكتوبر. كان هذا المؤتمر فرصة مميزة لتبادل الأفكار والمعرفة بين نخبة من الباحثين والأكاديميين المتخصصين في مجالات الدراسات الاجتماعية والتاريخية والقانونية، حيث تميز بالتنوع الفكري والتخصصي الذي يعكس تطور هذه المجالات الحيوية.

شهد المؤتمر مشاركات واسعة من باحثين من مختلف الجامعات والمؤسسات العلمية حول العالم، وأسهم في مناقشة العديد من القضايا المحورية التي تتعلق بالتحديات الاجتماعية والقانونية التي تواجه المجتمعات المعاصرة. كما تناولت الأبحاث المقدمة مواضيع تتعلق بالتاريخ وارتباطه بتشكيل البنى الاجتماعية والقانونية في الحاضر، مما أضفى بعداً تحليلياً معمقاً على المناقشات العلمية.

إن هذا الكتاب يضم بين دفتيه نتاج جهود بحثية متميزة أسهمت في تقديم رؤى نقدية ومعرفية حول قضايا متشابكة ومعقدة، مع السعي إلى تقديم حلول مستدامة للتحديات القانونية والاجتماعية القائمة. ولعل هذا التنوع في الأبحاث يعكس مدى أهمية المؤتمر في تعزيز التفاهم العلمي وتوسيع آفاق الحوار الأكاديمي بين الباحثين في مختلف التخصصات. نتمنى أن يجد القارئ في هذا الكتاب إضافة قيمة إلى المعرفة العلمية، وأن يساهم في تطوير الدراسات الاجتماعية والتاريخية والقانونية بما يعزز التقدم الفكري والاجتماعي للمجتمعات.

أنقرة – 2024/10/12

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The Image of Heaven in the Public Imagination through Al-Ma'arri's Epistle of Forgiveness (Risalah al-ghufran)

Dr. Öğretim Üyesi Esat Layek

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Abstract

This essay's abstract explores the representation of heaven in Al-Ma'arri's Epistle of Forgiveness and its influence on collective imagination, emphasizing the philosophical and religious concepts within the text. It examines how the epistle's portrayal of heaven shaped the cultural and intellectual climate of its time, as well as its reception in subsequent periods and its lasting impact on Islamic thought. The abstract also assesses the effect of Al-Ma'arri's work on contemporary and modern views of paradise, particularly its influence on literature and art. By presenting a unique depiction of heaven that challenges traditional beliefs, the epistle offers a compelling perspective. This overview delves into themes such as paradise, redemption, and the interconnectedness of heavenly and earthly life, while also addressing the concepts of reward and punishment in the afterlife, as depicted in Islamic theology.

Keywords: Al-Ma'arri. Risalah al-ghufran. Heaven.

El-Maari'nin Bağışlanma Risalesi'nde (Risaletü'l-Gufran) Halkın Hayalindeki Cennet Tasavvuru

Dr. Öğretim Üyesi Esat Layek

Tokat Gaziosmanpaşa Üniversitesi

Özet

Bu makalenin özeti, Al-Ma'arri'nin Bağışlama Mektubu'ndaki cennet tasvirini ve metindeki felsefi ve dini kavramları vurgulayarak kolektif tahayyül üzerindeki etkisini araştırıyor. Mektubun cennet tasvirinin, döneminin kültürel ve entelektüel iklimini nasıl şekillendirdiğini, sonraki dönemlerde nasıl karşılandığını ve İslam düşüncesi üzerindeki kalıcı etkisini inceliyor. Özet ayrıca Al-Ma'arri'nin eserinin çağdaş ve modern cennet görüşleri üzerindeki etkisini, özellikle edebiyat ve sanat üzerindeki etkisini değerlendiriyor. Geleneksel inançlara meydan okuyan benzersiz bir cennet tasviri sunarak, mektup ilgi

çekici bir bakış açısı sunuyor. Bu genel bakış, cennet, kurtuluş ve cennet ve dünya hayatının birbirine bağlılığı gibi temaları incelerken, aynı zamanda İslam teolojisinde tasvir edildiği gibi ahirette ödül ve ceza kavramlarını da ele alıyor.

Anahtar kelimeleri. Al-Ma'arri. Risalah Gufran. Cennet.

1. Introduction

The aim of this essay is to explore the transformation of the perception of heaven as a "risky" place in the public consciousness during the tenth century, as evidenced by a particular text. Although the concepts discussed are rooted in Islamic beliefs of that era, they have resonance beyond that context. Throughout time, heaven has been viewed as a perfect ideal that has sparked intellectual, spiritual, and creative endeavors. This is reflected in the ethical discussions about the definition of a "virtuous" individual and the methods to attain this state.

(Wakefield, 2020)(Hall, 2021)(Berry, 2021)(Laurie Brink, 2022)(Watson, 2023)(Faber, 2020)(AL-Shawaf & Zidan, 2023)(Boyd Jr, 2021)(Ganguly and Krishnan2022)(Tlostanova, 2020)

Epistle of Forgiveness, written by one of the most conspicuous poets of Islamic literature, Al-Ma'arri, provides a thought-provoking example of such remarkable heavenly descriptions. Al-Ma'arri occupied himself with other celestial matters by writing a dual poetic work after a near-death experience. It is a piece that impresses the reader with its richness of both form and subject matter and it is valued as a seminal work because of its rather unusual themes. The poet ushers his reader to the two sides of the afterlife, the respective punishment and reward. In contrast to the hellish outlines, Al-Ma'arri's heaven offers ample and idyllic details about the place where the just are supposed to end their torment. (Khalil, 2023)(Tamplin, 2020)(Dahiyat, 2023)(Morrissey, 2021)(Rihani, 2020)(Doğan)(ARAB, 2020)

In this study, I draw attention to the problems arising from the in-depth descriptions of Al-Ma'arri's heaven and pinpoint the unusuality to my knowledge of this work. The scrutinized content creates ambiguities that are difficult to explain, especially if one abides by the idea that heaven represents ideas and, by extension, the beliefs of the society where the creator of the piece lived. the text provides insight into the public perception of heaven and how it has evolved over time.

The concept of heaven has been a subject of fascination and intrigue for centuries, with various interpretations and depictions shaping the public imagination. Al-Ma'arri's Epistle of Forgiveness offers a unique perspective on this topic, presenting a thought-provoking portrayal of the afterlife that challenges traditional beliefs.

1.1. Background and Significance

Emile Tyan, the advisor of the Great Faisal, referred to the Epistle of Forgiveness as one of the most important sources of the uprising. In 523 AH, the poet and philosopher Al-Maarri completed the Epistle of Forgiveness, a verse-narrative that spans more than 5000 lines and relates the tale of a poet who dreams he is in the afterlife. In this cosmological fantasia, Al-Maarri entertains his readers with a whimsical account of his fantastic and unprecedented postmortal journey, both to the depths of Hell and up to the celestial delights of Paradise.

Through the Epistle of Forgiveness, Al-Maarri attempts to settle a century-long dispute between unorthodox and heterodox schools of thought. With profound skepticism, he describes what he regards as misinformed and superstitious conceptions of going to Heaven before eternity in a didactic manner that he paradoxically hopes will secure for himself this escape. (Hodgkin, 2023)(Thaver, 2024)

1.2. Purpose and Scope of the Study

In dealing with the question of inhibiting textual development, only the study of texts can provide us with reliable evidence. Inquiry into society is a complex and many-faceted endeavor, and it is just as unrealistic to assume that we can attempt to resolve all the issues that it throws up as it is to attempt to uncover all possible facets of a society through a single exploration. Because the elements of society are continually changing and dynamic, historical research is by its nature selective, as well as bound by constraints that are often frustratingly pernicious. If textual investigation is one possible way of accessing the beliefs, prejudices, and knowledge of societies, it remains the case in general terms that the beliefs, prejudices, and knowledge of many past societies are simply inaccessible. For many periods, lacking both text and archaeology, we possess very little indeed. The world of the imagination, which it has already been emphasized is as much a historical period transforms as the world of the hard-written texts, is frequently closed to us. (Deane, 2020)(Saux et al.2021)(Follmer & Tise, 2022)

Because the evidence of texts is so often the only way forward, it is imperative that we choose the texts that we examine. Again, the great mass of surviving text is not readily accessible or available, and some of it does not repay detailed study. The weight of all the words already written and preserved has long seemed prodigious even to those who have attempted to study in great depth one particular aspect of them. Even if more time is at our disposal every speech, play, sermon, tombstone inscription, song, letter, and exercise book from all the peoples of the past could be scrutinized in minute detail by a throng of trained epigraphists, archaic or scholarly, there is more writing than could ever be read, much less digested, and the making of choices is inescapable. Of these texts, the presence of more than 80 percent of them survives from a period extending from the fourth century to a still undefined time after present: the fourth century, the twelfth century, the fifteenth century, and so on, according to the several calendars

in which the modern Western world measures the passage of time. This is, needless to say, a very clear indication of which past civilizations especially fascinate the present. Other civilizations have bequeathed us just fractions of the textual legacy and yet are powerful generally and have something important to say. But the sheer size of these pagan, Christian, and Arabic storehouses confirms the understandable attraction of these cultures for many and explains why they continue to attract historians of so many varieties of persuasion and why different points of view in the present frequently appeal to the beliefs of the past. Given the problems and opportunities of the immense variety of texts available, the question is most frequently asked in one way or another: which represent the best or most revealing texts to study? What are the epistles of Jesus and his Brethren, the source and subject of the following chapters? (Putnam, 2024)(Marks, 2024)(Offenberg, 2024)(Lerer, 2020)(Mullett)

2. Al-Ma'arri: Life and Works

Chapter 2: Al-Ma'arri: Life and Works

"Abu al-'Ala Ahmed ibn 'Abdallah al-Ma'arri was born in Ma'arra, near Aleppo, in 363/973 and died in 450/1058. He was the 'simply sincere' poet and philosopher who made 'emptiness' his project, both in life and in poetry. And that is why a dual image emerges from his life: the hermit with his misanthropy, who preached not a system of ethical teachings, but 'the shame of belonging to the human race,' as Massignon stated, and who was ironic or hostile toward the great religions of the Arab world; and the pantheist philosopher, disciple of the Sufi Qannawi, who received and appreciated the teachings of the great Eastern and Western philosophers. The Egyptian biographers traced Ma'arri's genealogy back to the Prophet, whereas the Syrian biographers close to the poet show a certain diffidence toward the author of the Risalat al-ghufran, who appears to have been in contact with the Byzantium of that era."

2.1. Biographical Overview

This poem, like many other Arabic maqaamas or long poems, contains an intricate and sometimes confusing plot about the journey of its protagonist, a poet named Abu-l-'Ala al-Ma'arri, from Earth through the known Islamic cosmos. These include the aether, 7 heavens, Kursi, water, and mountains. The journey then continues to the limbo or barrier that connects two worlds and restricts communication between them, before returning back. These worlds, which have mutual political and social interaction, are similar to each other but represent two different types of authorities. In this case, they are the Muslim

and Byzantine ones. In the context of political Islamic theology, this takes place in the mythical Meccan City during the critical Islamic history of the beginning of Islam and the caliphate. (Khansa2022)

According to the predecessors and contemporaries of the poet, including al'Attar and al-Qazwini, sticking to this topic means that Ma'arri is critically discussing the politics of his Abbasid state and his hypocritical acceptance in poetry where he criticizes al-Ma'mun and his followers' opposition. However, the greatest paradox of the poem lies in the bitter arguments against those whose political concept Ma'arri's own ideas are very close to, and whose ruler, being a Muslim, is of course obliged to do everything written in the Holy book, including criticism of the image itself. We shall emphasize some characteristic situations within the historical framework in which the poem was written and use these remarks as a reference in the following discussion of the image of the afterlife. (Monroe, 2021)

2.2. Literary Contributions

Some historians have acknowledged and even praised the able role of the Umayyad and Abbasid statesmen, philosophers, and intellectuals. However, none see it beyond the religious framework within which these intellectuals worked based on their own beliefs. (Rahman, 2021)

However, if we approach the issue from a purely secular point of view, then undoubtedly the outcome of such religious beliefs would generate stronger and more steadfast personalities. This is exactly what the Umayyad and Abbasid caliphate needed, as they were running two major empires and facing enormous problems. It was a survival of the fittest for these people. Investment, arguing, and fluency in debates were the tools that determined who was the fittest.

Moreover, such confrontation and the diversity of Islamic religious sects and groups had an impact on various aspects of society's daily life. We read and hear about them in the sayings, actions, and even literature of that era. Religion gained deeper roots, a richer power of influence, and became a wide range that covered every aspect of daily life. It appeared on the Arab scene independent from the apotheosis of religious pre-Islamic beliefs, where it had its tentacles on every aspect of daily life. (Ammerman, 2020)(Schilling, 2022)

3. The Epistle of Forgiveness: Overview and Context

The Epistle of Forgiveness: Overview and Context

The worldview and spirituality of Islamic civilization can be observed by studying key texts such as al-Buḥṭh al-Mubḥr (The Clear Investigation) and the Risālah al-ghufrān (Epistle of Forgiveness) by Abu al-'Ala', the Muslim thinker born in Ahmad ibn 'Abdallah, on December 26, 973. While the first is distinguished by its boldness in rationalizing textual difficulties of the Qur'an and encouraging doubt as

the starting point in theological or other scientific progress, the second serves as a very long dialogue between two travelers as they journey between ends from the earth to the nearest heavens, while discussing lessons on life that emerge from different ways of rewarding the afterlife. Unlike the al-Buḥṭh, the Risālah is more focused on literary and existential issues, offering a wonderful view of the Islamic world. This work is unique in both its nature and its place in the intellectual history of the Muslims. It has a unique structure, introduces many poems and poems as well, intertwines narration and argument at high levels of narrative complexity, and is often linked to it, had considerable influence on later centuries. (Lindstedt, 2021)(Al-Husban et al.2024)

The act of writing as concise a summary of the Risālah as will appear, in this version, unfinished and insufficient given that the Risālah thematizes fundamental aspects of human life, from happiness by becoming the cause of unhappiness to the hope of salvation, in an accessible and complete manner. Consideration of the literary beauty of this manuscript, given that it is written in a unique, bellicose manner, reveals that its character is due to its subtle and extremely complex architecture. The reader embarks on a leisurely journey through delightfully relaxing traffic, stopping in meandering neighborhoods like experiencing a progressive and colorful account that ends with soma during an unsettling occult journey, which uses its objectives as a redeemer to promote these considerations without as friends acting formally, the texts contain a central nucleus as a mode that embellishes and gives life to all arguments. (Gruendler & Khalfallah, 2023)(al-Rahim et al.2023)(Meisami, 2020)(Altaş, 2021)

3.1. Summary of the Text

As we are currently focusing on a specific translated text in the context of a broader written culture, it might be helpful to provide a closer look at the text. This will enhance our understanding of the specific issues from different cultural and language perspectives. Yet, this cannot be very deep as long sections of the text are cited for other purposes. It will be important here to highlight the important aspects of the text, both its plot and main characteristics, so as to prepare the reader for the in-depth analysis that is to follow. The context of the text can aid in discerning what themes and preoccupations are of concern to the author, thereby drawing attention to the differences in the cultural background of the author and the reader. The reason for the text at the concordant stage of development in the hands of several powers draws important attention to the policies, the polyphonic nature of the text, and their relevance to the study.

The Epistle of Forgiveness is written by Abu al-Ala al-Ma'arri, a blind Arab philosopher who lived in modern-day Syria more than a thousand years ago. It talks of two friends: 'Isa ben Hisham, who embarks on a sea voyage from al-Jabiyah to Tilmin, and al-Mutanabbi, who boards a different ship on the same

journey. The course of their travel takes a number of unexpected twists, and the two friends eventually reach Jabarut, a califated land in which Adamic inhabitants inhabit. The reader is taken on a journey through the landscape of the afterlife through the imaginations of medieval Arabs with the plot. Several of the authors from this era, including al-Ma'arri, were horrified by the normative images of heaven and ventured to create an alternative for them. The text is 126 pages, written in rhymed prose. The first half of the text is written from the viewpoint of the unbeliever 'Isa ben Hisham, while the second half is written from the viewpoint of the righteous believer al-Mutanabbi. The author emphasized many sections in the narrative repeatedly not to make the reader mishear the ambiguous passages.

3.2. Historical and Cultural Context

Political and moral contexts are reflected in the public and private spaces through many types of representations. In the medieval Islamic world, poetry and written texts were regarded as some of the most effective ways to educate society. Public imagination was achieved through theater, poetry, architecture, and other arts. Cultural norms inevitably infiltrated depictions of heaven in public and religious documents, such as the Quran and Prophetic Hadiths, and in the everyday activities of the elite. Muslim authors were discouraged from speaking ill of heaven because of the fear of divine punishment. Despite the potential trouble that stemmed from overstepping the boundary and going to extremes, these depictions of otherworldly spaces allowed for court entertainment and philosophical analysis. (Muassomah et al.2020)

It was then not surprising that views of heaven began to appear in more secular treatment during the Abbasid period. This time could undoubtedly be called an interplay of ideas because of multicultural interaction between the Muslim, Christian, and Jewish worlds. Opinions of thinkers from these three communities about the heavenly eternity were written down or published, no matter whether these thinkers were direct participants in the discussion or these views were borrowed from earlier texts. There were four outstanding Arabic compositions about heaven during the time of the Abbasid Caliphate: the "Fountain of Wisdom," the "Refinement of the Merits," the "Pearl of Wonder," and the two "Epistles of Ikhwan al-Safa" and the "Epistle of Forgiveness" by Abu al-Ala'a and Ibn al-Qarih. "The Epistle of Ikhwan al-Safa," also known as the "Epistle of the Brothers of Purity," was compiled from the translated works of others. The Risalat al-Ghufran by Abu al-Ala'a gave a face for the first time to the hedonistic society of Baghdad, but it was through the Epistle of Forgiveness by the heretic Abu al-'Ala'a that a realistic image of the court life of the time of Caliph al-Mutawakkil shone, covered by a dark theatrical mask.

4. Heavenly Imagery in Al-Ma'arri's Epistle

This article will focus on the representation of heaven and the heavenly in an eleventh-century Arabic text titled *Risalet al-Dhahab* (Epistle of Forgiveness) by Abu al-'Ala' Ahmad ibn 'AbdAllah ibn Sulayman al-Ma'arri. For al-Ma'arri, writing on both the heavenly and the lower earthly worlds was not purely a theoretical journey, although it has often been presented as one. It was, to a large extent, a matter of contextually and tactically manipulating already existing modes and metaphors that were pertinent to each of the two worlds. Although the epistle has been critically studied, the scholarly treatment it has received is still quite minimal, and its messages and their numerous implications have largely been left unexplored. Indeed, this is the only detailed study of al-Ma'arri's heavenly imagery in *Risalet al-Dhahab*, and readers are reminded that in the future, more research based on comparative studies of medieval societies in various countries, including Spain, is needed to identify the sociocultural, socioecological, and mental contexts of the afterlife and its inhabitants. (Ahmad et al., 2020)

Al-Ma'arri lived in al-Anat, a town in Bilad Namrud, the land of Nimrod, in the south of the region between the two rivers (Mesopotamia). Although he was known for his urge to elevate morality in humans by revealing the truth and casting light on it, a quick look at the figurative painting in this world will reveal that the poet is wandering not only on the earth and in life but also seeking other places and other forms of representation. The resurrection, the great assembly in Paradise, shall awaken the spirits. But the martyrs will find paradise and grape blossoms. Wine will cause stress in that it shall flow from their bin. They shall drink from that bin and shall find divine affection. They leave the sky where the bin is located and follow it. Their pace shall be the gradual movement of clouds. The verses I assume now show not only the image the poet presents to us but also the ability of Arabic, a mythological metaphorical language, to create a clear and visible image of paradise. (Khodjamkulov et al.2020)

4.1. Key Themes and Motifs

Al-Ma'arri addresses a number of themes throughout the Epistle. The themes are not uniform but rather act as punctuation marks within the text, introducing a variety of digressions which serve to illustrate key points. We have attempted to classify these themes or motifs, and over the course of the Epistle, we determine that al-Ma'arri addresses discussions regarding theology, society, morality, literature, and aspects of anticlericalism and the freethinker. The epithet "A wren among swans" can be accurately applied to al-Ma'arri. He shares the same face as others of his kind but, in contrast to his fellow men, al-Ma'arri uses his intellect to observe and question the true nature of man and God. These observations define his free spirit, which is clandestinely confined within a predetermined framework of religious orthodoxy. (Muassomah et al.2020)

Al-Ma'arri discusses theological issues throughout the Epistle, including details of Islamic history and contradictions and ambiguities emanating from the Quran. His sociopolitical beliefs are a source of controversy and a potential contradiction, as one may be inclined to believe that within an Islamic framework, justice is not hindered but perfected. Al-Ma'arri expounds the belief that an unjust ruler will invariably meet his fate. Allah wills the quality type of ruler, and an unjust ruler will, in due course, become an anachronism. In the event that divine retribution is unpopular, unjust rulers are eliminated by their kith and kin. United Arab socialism, fascism, and brutal theocratic rule are manifestations of the same principle: the Islamic state is embryonic, and embryonic states are governed by strong-arm policy. Al-Ma'arri contends that "one who accuses God of the vices of man crashes himself." The freethinker perhaps envisions infallibility in human relics, thus negating the spiritual whole or higher intelligence ruling over ordinary mortals.

5. Public Perception and Reception of Heaven in Al-Ma'arri's Work

Al-Ma'arri's work was not solely religious; he integrated scientific, literary, historical, and religious materials to express his thoughts. His intended readers were the public reader, and he made use of satire as a method to question the outlook by the orthodox side. However, his work was welcomed mostly by the scholarly elite. In the Arabic Islamic world, the general public had a less solid connection to Paradise. Meanwhile, Heaven was regulated in the religious text and the pedestal collection produced by the religious scholars. Besides this, a variety of conducts about the Heaven and otherworld has been creased by the schismatic movements, which were considered as emergent, yet were disdained by the materials left by the authority. Creating the institution of the hereafter, "Epistle of Forgiveness" has been undermined, as an apparent detail of the period it was penned. (Lindstedt, 2021)(Grigoryan, 2022)(Diyāb et al.2022)(Lacey, 2021)(Dahiyat, 2023)(Elmeligi, 2023)(Moreh, 2023)

Despite Shiite consensus, "Epistle of Forgiveness" has been cited in the Sunni resources too, whether sympathy or mix-up. It has reopened the platform. Some Hanaefi scholars quoted the work, especially relying on the indefinite accounts about the Prophet with a critical general tendency. Ibn Jawzy's mentioning of the work, in his broad and impressive "Al-Maudu'ati", has taken note with a sharp style. Ibn Taymiyyah delved into it afterwards, notwithstanding a more reduced content than the previous ones. In the books of "Seredj ad-Din", where he summarized Ibn Jawzy by leap, he insisted on amplifying some of Ibn Jawzy's weak information. Later in the summaries of Ibn Al-Kaysan, it was claimed that the work was completely forgotten, even though similar approach by other scholars ascertains the opposite way. Nonetheless, the edifice was often dismissed from inserted into the religious section of the Sufism literature. The Sufi scholars had run aground in position when the working literature of either religious or mystical been detected against them. They would have orated it to the public with the feeling of

intolerant even tastelessness. Because they knew the language of the judiciary dissent, which they accepted without hesitation. Even in the mystical institutions would have shaken them. The Sunni Sufis generally did not want material mentioned, and the Shiite Sufis did not want it mixing up their fabricated theosophy. (Sevara and Abdunazarova2020)

5.1. Contemporary Views on Heaven

By showing his knowledge of Greek and Latin literature during his time and even after his era, al-Ma'arri's name was often mentioned in treatises on comparative literature. But for a long time, his works were not studied for their own sake. The Arabic Biographical Dictionary of Yaqūt, which was published around 626/1229, has no separate article on al-Ma'arri or, like most of the Liwa B: Claf, mentions only titles of his works and not the works themselves. Good examples of such a Modernist view are to be found in “what has been discovered about al-Javfi of Morat: his birth, his teachings and his disciples, his compendium of logical syllabus and his marginal notes. They seem to be lacking in originality, but the situation should not be reduced to nothing.

As a result of the lack of interest in all his complex writings and their interpretation, he was considered for a long time as a “Socialist who hates religious opinions” and equipped with a “penetrating intelligence.” The discussion about al-Ma'arri's views and therefore about the meaning to be assigned to the clearly ironical and provocative images for which he is famous. But to concentrate exclusively on the negation of religion and therefore on the promotion of ethical integrity seems to us simply wrong. We can verify, at this point, to which degree the denigration of the first aspect may have been due to our preconceived opinions. It is not the aim of this presentation to re-establish the importance of al-Ma'arri as a critical writer, the discussion on his place in the Islamic world, or even less to the discussion of his negation of cosmology and of the world. It will solely be limited to analyzing the image of Heaven found in that text, and we will also try to understand the meaning that may be given to such paintings. To reach that end, we will only show, first, the importance al-Ma'arri gives to the description of 'Anaza then how the poetic digression follows. To highlight the unique character of his own representation, we will then compare it with several known Near Eastern paradises of that time.

5.2. Critiques and Interpretations

It is fascinating that many Sufi mystics, without caring about its detrimental effect, swear by the Epistle of Forgiveness and Maārrī's attack on the image of heaven. They interpret the poem to be a part of Maārrī's spiritual journey in pursuit of truth. Preference for philosophical knowledge over religious rituals and ascetic practices is also interpreted to be the pundit's enlightenment in Sufi terms. It is always remarkable to note how most atheist scholars determine his thoughts and practices. If Maārrī were a

Western poet, his poem would have been universalized or secularized similar to that done with Lucretius. By virtue of the fact that Lucretius was a westerner, we find many sympathizers including some sublime poets turning a poet against spiritual darkness into a secular poet of romantic beauty! Such is the double standard of Western scholarship and sympathizers of atheist literature.

Al-Kindi, who is seen as the very first great proponent of classical Islamic ethical system, defends people's attraction to a garden-based heaven and a tree-based hell to help people who have no understanding of the rewards of the two Gardens Paradise and the Fire deepest Dungeon either spiritually or through the reinforcement of the idea of eternal life. Maārrī also tries to increase the faith among the believers by attacking heaven through religious Doxa to achieve the results that he desired. However, he has not impressed the atheist community because his well thought ideas were framed within religious rhetorics which they fiercely resist. Then there are theists who also disagree with Maārrī, arguing that belief in the heaven and hell (Pul Sirāt) in the afterlife is necessary ingredients of religious discipline and for the good order of the city of al-Maa(star)arrī.

6. Comparative Analysis with Other Works on Heaven

The image of heaven in the public imagination is presented vividly by authors of all times and in all languages: Apuleius, Dante, Milton, and Rabelais. It is interesting how heaven is depicted in the Muslim and Christian cultures of the East and the West in the context of public consciousness: in the "Epistle of Forgiveness" by al-Ma'arri, a medieval era poet, literary critic, teacher of Arabic and ancient poetry, in other medieval Arabic-era works, in Dante's "The Divine Comedy", and in other works such as "Al-Maqamah" by Hamadani. The article attempts to analyze whether there was a link between the authors' mentalities, the civilizations they belonged to, and the peculiarities of their religions.

The article provides an in-depth analysis of the "Epistle of Forgiveness" by al-Ma'arri in the context of the theory of comparative literary research. It discusses the problem of 'historical truth' about the author, his worldview, his perception of the conflicts of good and evil in the context of the period of his time. The article studies the philosophical aspect of his work; besides, it also provides a comparative study of the "Converter" and the "Epistle of Forgiveness" by al-Ghaza'li. The paper demonstrates the specifics of the Christian and Islamic paradises, as well as the authors' ideas about heaven, as well as the church and the mosque. In addition, the research analyzes the connection between the outlook of Dante and Al-Ma'arri in the context of the ideological platform, the eschatological image of their civilizations, religious paradises, and ideas of heaven. It examines the concept of the satire-ironic in cross-cultural communication, mainly focusing on the specific character of the religious and civilizational parodies in

Dante's "Divine Comedy", "Epistle of Forgiveness" by al-Ma'arri, "Al-Maqamah" by Hamadani and the image of the church and the mosque in the culture of the Arabic Middle Ages and the Italian Renaissance.

6.1. Similarities and Differences

We shall discuss the similarities and differences between the image of Heaven in the Islamic tradition and al-Ma'arri's vision of it, derived from his freedom of thought and speech. The description of Heaven as a paradisiacal garden can be found in the works of the Persian Sufi Abul Hasan Al-Nuri as well as in al-Ghazzali's *Al-Rassail Al-Lukiyya*. Anwar Abdul-Latif has described the descriptions of Heaven by Muslim reformers and sufis. A further source to explore the image of Heaven in the Islamic tradition is Al-Zaid's Epistle of Heaven. All these sources describe Heaven as a paradisiacal garden with rivers and fruit trees, filled with palaces preceded by chambers, decorated with pure gold, full of pearls and jacinth.

It is noted that everyone who enters Heaven would have the pleasure of all beauties of the palace. Similar images also appear in Sunni poems. This traditional understanding of Heaven is totally different from what we read in al-Ma'arri's work. Contrary to the Islamic tradition, al-Ma'arri's idea of Heaven is not a paradisiacal place with rivers and trees in which the most important thing is the food with which palaces are filled. Therefore, his work is not a mirror of the sensual paradise which we may find in other works, in particular the Sunni poems.

7. Impact and Legacy of Al-Ma'arri's Depiction of Heaven

To assess the extent to which Ma'arr's negative depiction of Heaven has indeed been etched into the public imagination over a millennium of intensive religious orthodoxy, despite considerable evidence of mainstream opposition, we postpone any direct discussion of Ma'arri until Chapter 4. However, suggesting a negative answer to the Nauman puzzle can hardly be regarded as ground-breaking. Trusting rhetoric as an unintended or even undesirable verandah for such enduring ideas may seem improbable, but both offer a mechanism adaptable enough for successful survival and replication of beliefs contrary to the conventional wisdom.

Debunking Heaven most certainly did not start with Ma'arri. Nor has it been universally condemned as a disastrous and futile enterprise in futility. Hermann Nohl, rehabilitating the libertine critic Lucian in the early 1930s as a religious philosopher, provided a detailed comparison between heaven as depicted by the "weepy and naïve Christian propagandists" and "the solid and reliable heaven out of which 'the malicious irony of the pagan' looks" based on the example of an old and well-respected critic. That is, an important idea was formulated more than a millennium before Ma'arr's time regarding the intellectual properties of heaven, having how vast communications between the human experience and different iterations of heaven will be firmly notion of heaven feature in the perspective of the public imagination.

This chapter provides a brief summary of some of the predictable dynamics influencing the thoughts and opinions regarding the past and then identifies where Ma'arr stands.

7.1. Literary Influence

To appreciate al-Ma'arri's polemics about heaven, one needs to understand his own literary heritage. On the one hand, his protest and outrage against heaven and its delights are motivated by Islam and the assumptions of the secular world in which he lived. On the other hand, justifying the validity of employing the idealized images of paradise, al-Ma'arri utilized the language, images, and topoi of literary traditions. This chapter attempts to represent the several literary strands of al-Ma'arri's heritage in order to seek out possible threads that are likely to penetrate and structure the author's victimized amusement at the painted dreams of the pious. Hellenic and Islamic traditions are represented in a vast body of literature based on fictitious voyages to unattainable realms. They offered a luminous ideal of existence on a forbidden or inaccessible land as well as illustrated motifs of the long-lasting legend of the earthly paradise. Parishes or utopias, often depicted in the traditions of poetic travel, function as gates to enter a mysterious world of imagination that reflected man's optimistic dreams of living separately from the real world.

Rising after literary oblivion from such travel fictions of the Late Antiquity as the "Napian Hypnerotomachia," "De Mirabilibus Auscultationibus" by Philostratus, "Zetus" by Lucian, and others, both interpreters from Baghdad, the maestro and creator of "A Thousand and One Nights," seized the works in which the earthly paradise was depicted as a real place, full of naturalistic references to the earthly life. These Arab tradition-keeping writers are Al-Ġahiz, the author of "Marvels of the Created" and "The Book of the Proprieties." They left a significant mark in the thinking of the native Levantine Syrian writer-Philosopher al-Ma'arri who flourished and polished their naturalistic descriptions of Utopia. The theme of "the attainability of the unattainable" in literature likens al-Ma'arri to the Syrian writer and thinker, an outstanding figure of the Golden Age of the Umayyad, the philologist, natural scientist, and freedman of the Umayyad Caliphate, Al-Ġahiz. They employed the travel story as a tool to wag a finger at the superficiality and shortcomings of society's morality, satirizing the religious perversions of the time.

7.2. Cultural and Religious Implications

The philosophical, ethical, and religious implications of both Jabir and Al-Ma'arri's travels into Heaven are tightly interwoven together. The text has been divided into two main geohistorical contexts in which the main actors of the story, al-Ma'mun and al-Rumya, whose story is mingled with human historical and scientific material. Another important conclusion that may be drawn here is that al-Ma'arri, by

choosing to narrate it at all in the form and fashion in which he does, conveys some important implications through his word choices and other elements supporting narrative structure.

The story also draws out attempts made by rationalists like Jabir Ibn Hayyan and Al-Ma'arri regarding the seeability of the noos or divine intellect and the relationship between the active intellect and the primary four Aristotelian causes. The pairing of Al-Ma'mun and his vizier with the Baron is seen to reverse the roles of the omnipotent god and his preacher who lectures about Hell, thereby reflecting the Weltanschauung at the time that in the 10th century, Al-Ma'mun's Islamic Kingdom was so close to Heaven reinforcing God's will that it will mirror Christian Heaven in all its details.

8. Conclusion

Eliot was right concerning the wide appeal of Al-Ma'arri's work. His observation, however, requires clarification and this is undoubtedly achieved primarily due to the narrative scope and detail of The Epistle of Forgiveness. Broadly, when discussing perceptions of the afterlife, heaven continues to be an important topic. As discussed in Jurgen Wasim Frembgen's "Metaphors and their Use in Popular Islam", the idea of the repasts of Paradise is prominently played out in his study of the Pakistani public sphere and popular piety. Strong limiting, feminist and feminizing interpretations of Paradise reveal ideological and structural aspects of popular beliefs. (Grigoryan, 2022)(Moreh, 2023)(Monroe, 2021)

Al-Ma'arri himself suggests in this work that one should attempt to make sense of Paradise in a metaphorical sense and use the images of Heaven to create an ideal in this world. The public imagination of heaven and future life is more welcoming, however, for despite all the criticism the texts of flood and female sensuality provide a sense of hope within concepts of heaven in the public imagination. It continues to fulfill a function in the social lives of the living by highlighting certain privileges and rewards for moral deeds.

8.1. Key Findings and Insights

This chapter has covered a study that attempted to bridge a theoretical gap which exists in understanding material-epistemic assumptions that are embedded in individuals' worldview and their everyday responses to world problems. Specifically, the study argued that the public imagination, that is, the shared images, dreams, and hopes of social groups, constitutes an important gender postulate towards understanding world problems and the tendencies which these groups assume in mitigating them. The argument was operationalized by evaluating the shared celestial imagination attributed to a group of people alluded to as secular-humans.

In examining this assumption for the Islamic tradition, al-Ma'arri's Epistle of Forgiveness, as one of the prominent sources of the celestial imagination of heaven, was used. The analysis shows a balance of abundance and exquisite beauty among the extreme sensate-hedonist experience, which contradicts extremist asceticism and refusal of the physical body in classical Islamic thought. This balanced vision of reward served sociopolitical ends for the Buyid vizier and the Muslim elite, helping to immortalize them in paradise, and may have also addressed popular criticisms of their less-than-exemplary lifestyles. Al-Ma'arri responds to the powerful hidden cultural undercurrent in Islam and many other religions that asserts spiritual worth greatly exceeds bodily worth, and that spiritual discipline, rather than physical pleasure, earns religious merits.

8.2. Future Research Directions

There are several aspects of interest for future researchers. One overarching question is to explore the interconnections between al-Ma'arri's blend of unique extremes and his philosophy at large. Are all people of the blend of unique extremes proto-humanists? If so, what do the other positions in the competition represent? In addition to that, the aspectarian backstories of the various characters of the blend of unique extremes are fascinating as well. Why is Zayd bin 'Amr more informed about religious truth than other Muslims? Furthermore, given that al-Ma'arri - writing in the second half of the 10th century - has no qualms about attributing Homo neanderthalensis to the blend of unique extremes and that so many pieces of religious and philosophical literature have been lost since then, how many of the aspectarian backstories actually match the theologies/philosophies of their time?

Apart from exploring the philosophical aspects of the work, a future researcher may explore in detail al-Ma'arri's literary strategy. In particular, it might make sense to look at which aspect of his characters' multifacetedness al-Ma'arri is willing to use as an argument. Perhaps he tried to create negative associations with being a dirham viewer/skinflint coward and timeless to various extent.

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